

ISic2936

I.Sicily inscription 2936

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

volcanic lava stone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Hybla Gereatis

Place of origin (modern)

Paternò

Provenance

Said by Orsi in 1900 to have been found 'recently' in the garden of the (ex) convent of the Cappuccini, Paternò , although Soraci 1958 notes that a reading is attributed to a local antiquarian c.1808

Coordinates

37.562836, 14.893780

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

described by Orsi as a 'dado' (i.e. a base without moulding, or with the moulding missing?), with a circular cavity in the upper surface

Dimensions

Height 36 cm

Width 57 cm

Depth 36 cm

Layout

Greek text on the front face, on three lines

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. Γυμνασιάρχης
2. Εύβουλίδας
3. Ἡρακλείου

Apparatus

Text after Orsi 1900, but corrected

Cordiano notes the oddity of line 1 and speculates that we should read

Γυμνασιάρχης[ας]

Orsi: ΕΥΚΟΥΛΙΔΑΣ

Translation (en)

Gymnasiarch Euboulidas, son of Herakleios

Commentary

The origin of the stone is uncertain, found together with ISic2946, according to Orsi, in the garden of the former convent for the Cappuchins, in the late C19 AD; however both are apparently reported in earlier antiquarian texts (see Soraci 1958, and Manganaro 1963), and Manganaro speculates that both perhaps come originally from nearby Civita, thought possibly to be the site of ancient Aetna-Inessa.

Digital identifiers:

TM 644845

EDCS 70900783

EDCS 70900828

Bibliography

Orsi, P. 1900. Frammenti epigrafici sicelioti. *Rivista di storia antica*. 5: 39-66. At 55 no.28

Soraci, R. 1958. Appunti di epigrafia greca e romana relativa alla regione hyblense-inessea-adranita. *Rendiconti dell'Accademia Nazionale dei Lincei. Classe di Scienze morali, storiche e filologiche*. 7.13: 251-257. At 253

Manganaro, G. 1963. Nuove ricerche di epigrafia siceliota. *Siculorum Gymnasium*. 16: 51-64. At 57

Cordiano, G. 1997. La ginnasiarchia nelle "poleis" dell'occidente mediterraneo antico. *Studi e testi di storia antica* 7. Pisa. At 38-39

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic2936. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4356482>